

JCMST 2018

THE 1ST PSU-UNS JOINT CONFERENCE
ON MEDICAL SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY 2018

5th-7th March 2018
Krabi, Thailand

organized by
Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University
and University of Novi Sad, Serbia

In conjunction with
The 5th Joint Symposium BMS-BME-EU
Post-graduate Health Science & Technology Conference

Qualitative analysis of simvastatin metabolites arising from probiotic bacteria - *in vitro* study

Maja Đanić^{1*}, Nebojša Pavlović², Saša Vukmirović¹, Bojan Stanimirov²,
Gordana Bojić³, Svetlana Goločorbin-Kon², Momir Mikov¹

¹Department of Pharmacology, Toxicology and Clinical Pharmacology,
Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad

²Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

³Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Medicine,
University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Email: maja.djanic@mf.uns.ac.rs

Introduction: Gut microflora may be considered as a special organ with huge metabolic activity that may be the cause of interindividual differences in drugs response. Therefore, the implication of the microbiome variations in personalized medicine and in pharmacomicrobiomics is becoming an interesting topic of many research investigations. Simvastatin is a lipid-regulating drug that is administered as a prodrug in a form of lactone and needs to be activated chemically or enzymatically in human body. To date, several studies have reported that there exist interindividual differences in response to simvastatin, which are only partially explained by genetic factors. Due to emerging role of gut microflora and probiotic bacteria in drug metabolism, the aim of the study was to examine their role in simvastatin metabolism and to identify metabolites formed in that way, since there is no available data yet on this topic in literature.

Materials and methods: Our study was performed *in vitro*. After incubation of simvastatin solution (50 ug/mL) with mixture of probiotic bacteria *Lactobacillus acidophilus* and *Bifidobacterium longum* (10⁸/ml) for twenty four hours, Liquid Chromatography - Tandem Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) with data-dependent scanning was applied for the qualitative and semiquantitative analysis of simvastatin metabolites. Intracellular, extracellular and total content was analysed. Molecular descriptors related to physicochemical properties and pharmacokinetic behavior were calculated using VolSurf+ software.

Results: After incubation period with probiotic bacteria, concentration of simvas-

tatin has been decreased by 44.1%. At the same time, eight simvastatin metabolites were identified. Metabolites share some of the common fragment ions in MS² spectra with simvastatin (m/z 303, 285, 267, 243, 225, 199, 173) confirming the origin of these compounds. Metabolites were generated by several bacterial enzymatic reactions catalysed by esterases, dehydratases, dehydrogenases, demethylases and hydroxylases. According to calculated physico-chemical properties, some of metabolites remained more out of bacteria and some of them concentrated more intracellularly. The major metabolite was hydroxylated metabolite of simvastatin hydroxy acid. This metabolite showed quite improved physico-chemical and pharmacokinetic properties compared to simvastatin.

Conclusions: Our results suggest that selected bacterial strains *Lactobacillus acidophilus* and *Bifidobacterium longum* are involved in the metabolism of simvastatin. Further *in vivo* studies are needed in order to provide more detailed insight into the pharmacological and toxicological properties of proposed metabolites. In addition, future research is required to elucidate the contribution of gut microflora and probiotics to interindividual differences in simvastatin response.

Keywords: simvastatin, gut microflora, probiotics, drug metabolism, data-dependent scanning